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New One Versus^{All}_{One} Method: NOV@

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Abstract

Binarization strategies decompose the original multi-class dataset into multiple two-class subsets, learning a different binary model for each new subset. One-vs-One (OVO) and One-vs-All (OVA) are two of the most well-known techniques: One-vs-One separates a pair of classes in each binary sub-problem, ignoring those remaining; and One-vs-All distinguishes one class from all the other classes. In this paper, we present two new OVO and OVA combinations where the best base classifier is applied in each sub-problem of both cases. The first presented is called OVA+OVO since it combines the outputs obtained by OVO and OVA decomposition strategies. The second combination we denominate as *New One Versus*^{All}_{One} (NOV@), and the objective is to solve the problems that we have found in OVA when different base classifiers are used in each sub-problem. In order to validate the performance of the new proposal, an empirical study has been carried out where the two new methods are compared with other well-known decomposition strategies of the literature. Experimental results show that both methods obtain promising results, especially NOV@.

Keywords: Decomposition Strategies, One against One, One against All

1. Introduction

The goal in a supervised classification problem consists of classifying the new unlabelled example x in its correct class using a training set. Let $TR = \{x_i, \theta_i\}_{i=1}^N$ denote a training set of N well-labelled examples, where x_i represents i -th individual feature vector and θ_i represents the class which that individual belongs to. In the particular case of the K -class problem, being $\theta \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, the class label is commonly defined as an integer. Based on the TR , the supervised classification techniques create a “general rule” or a function which is used to classify the new unlabelled case. This general rule is also known as a classifier.

For some kind of classifiers, such as SVM, it is much more easier to build a classifier to distinguish only between two classes. However, many real world problems are multi-class problems, i.e. $K > 2$. In view of that, there are some techniques which divide the original multi-class problem into many binary classification problems. These are known as class-binarization techniques. These techniques are two-step methods: in the first step a classifier is learned for each of these sub-problems, and in the second step the outputs of these classifiers are combined to obtain the final prediction.

There are three different class-binarization strategies: “One vs One” (OVO), “One vs All” (OVA) and “Error Correcting Output Codes” (ECOC), where OVO and OVA are the most common in the literature due to their simplicity and clarity.

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- One vs One (OVO) [10]: In each sub-problem only the cases belonging to two classes are compared between them, ignoring those remaining.
- One vs All (OVA) [2]: In each sub-problem one class is compared with the rest of classes.
- Error Correcting Output Codes (ECOC) [7]: In each sub-problem all the classes are grouped into two groups, and the two groups are compared between them.

In binary classification strategies the classical way is to use the same base classifier for each binary sub-problem, but it is possible that the selected base classifier could have difficulties correctly discriminating in some of those sub-problems, thus it obtains incorrect results. However, this drawback could be solved by treating each sub-problem as an independent classification problem, thereby it is possible to use a different base classifier for each sub-problem.

In this paper, we propose two new combinations of the methods OVO and OVA. We have compared these two methods with other class-binarization strategies over 20 UCI databases, obtaining promising results. In all methods we try to find the best base classifiers for each sub-problem. To do that, we have chosen several well-known classifiers from different Machine Learning paradigms: SVM, C4.5 Decision Tree, Ripper, K-NN, Multilayer Perceptron and Naive Bayes. The first combination that we have proposed is called OVA+OVO. OVA+OVO basically combines the sub-problems obtained after the OVO and OVA methods are applied. Comparing this new method with other class-binarization strategies we have realized that some of these strategies, such as OVA, are not appropriate to use when different base classifiers are used in each sub-problem. As a consequence, we propose a second approach that we have called *New One Versus One*^{All} (NOV@). NOV@ is an extension of OVA: at decomposition time OVA is applied, whereas at combination time the majority vote is used to take the final decision. When there are draws among some classes, OVO is applied for tie-breaking only taking into account the draw classes.

In the specialized literature, there exist few works that select the best base classifier for each sub-problem. And none of these works compares different class-binarization techniques in order to observe how each technique works. In our work we have also compared the two new methods with other state-of-the-art class-binarization strategies in order to perform an empirical study.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we review the decomposition techniques, with special attention to OVO and OVA strategies while Section 3 is devoted to related works. In Section 4 we show the preliminary work to motivate the combination of OVO and OVA strategies. The first proposed method is introduced in Section 5 and Section 6 shows the experimental results obtained. Section 7 presents the second motivation where the weaknesses of some strategies are shown. Section 8 describes our second approach and Section 9 shows the results of the experiments carried out. Finally, Section 10 states the conclusions of our work and future research lines.

2. Class-Binarization

Class-binarization is composed of two steps: decomposition and combination.

In the decomposition step the original problem is divided into several binary sub-problems. The most popular strategies consist of grouping classes, in this way each binary classifier compares two groups of classes between them. Commonly the code-matrix is used to represent how the classes are grouped.

Figure 1 shows a code-matrix example, where each row represents a class and each column represents a binary classifier. Each class takes values in the set $\{-1,0,+1\}$, where $+1$ indicates the classes associated to the positive-class, -1 indicates the classes associated to the negative-class and 0 indicates that the class is ignored for this binary problem. In Figure 1 how a 5-class problem $\{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4, \theta_5\}$ is decomposed into 5 binary problems $\{f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5\}$ can be seen. For instance, it can be seen that the classifier f_1 is constructed in such a manner that the cases belonging to θ_1 and θ_2 are grouped in class $+1$ and the cases in θ_3 and θ_5 in class -1 . So this classifier compares θ_1 and θ_2 classes with θ_3 and θ_5 , while the cases that belong to θ_4 are ignored.

In classification time, each binary classifier returns a prediction. So the combination step consists of combining these predictions. Therefore, it is crucial to select a proper combination of the outputs in order to make a correct prediction.

Different decomposition strategies have been developed. Two of the most popular are OVO and OVA, which are described next.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{classes} \\
\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \theta_1 \\ \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 \\ \theta_4 \\ \theta_5 \end{array} \right.
\end{array}
\begin{array}{c}
\overbrace{\text{classifiers}} \\
\begin{array}{c} f_1 \ f_2 \ f_3 \ f_4 \ f_5 \\
\left(\begin{array}{ccccc} 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \end{array} \right)
\end{array}
\end{array}
\begin{array}{l}
f_1 \rightarrow \theta_1, \theta_2 \text{ vs } \theta_3, \theta_5 \\
f_2 \rightarrow \theta_2, \theta_3 \text{ vs } \theta_4, \theta_5 \\
f_3 \rightarrow \theta_3 \text{ vs } \theta_1, \theta_2 \\
f_4 \rightarrow \theta_4 \text{ vs } \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_5 \\
f_5 \rightarrow \theta_2 \text{ vs } \theta_5
\end{array}$$

Figure 1: Example of a code matrix

2.1. One Vs All (OVA)

2.1.1. Decomposition

OVA decomposition scheme divides a K class multi-class problem, $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_K$, into K two-class problems, where each binary problem discriminates one class from the others.

In Figure 2(a) OVA's code matrix for 4 classes can be seen: in each classifier one class is represented as positive class while all the other 3 classes are represented as negative-class.

2.1.2. Combination

As one class is compared with all the other classes, most of the binary sub-problems are unbalanced. It is known that one of the drawbacks of an unbalanced problem is the underestimation for the minority classes, thereby the most represented class is selected in most cases. In view of that, in OVA it is very common that all sub-problems return a class-negative prediction, hence, it is usual for there to be ties in the final decision when the majority vote is used. Thus, it is more common to use the confidence level of each classifier to decide the final output. The class with the highest confidence is that which is selected.

2.2. One Vs One (OVO)

2.2.1. Decomposition

OVO decomposition scheme divides a K class multi-class problem, $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_K$, into $K(K-1)/2$ two-class sub-problems. In each sub-problem a classifier is learned using only the cases that belong to a pair of classes (θ_i, θ_j) , where $\theta_i \neq \theta_j$; the remaining cases are ignored.

In Figure 2(b) OVO's code matrix for 4 classes can be seen: in each classifier one class is represented as +1 class, another is represented as -1 and the remaining 2 classes are represented as 0.

Compared with OVA, it can be observed that OVO creates more sub-problems. Moreover, the disadvantage of having so many sub-problems is that most of them are irrelevant and they are forced to give wrong answers for many instances, because each classifier must assign every pattern to one of two classes. If a pattern belongs to class i , all the classifiers that are not trained to differentiate this class will cast wrong votes. However, OVO uses fewer examples in each sub-problem and thus has more freedom for fitting a decision boundary between the two classes.

2.2.2. Combination

The simplest way to combine the outputs is to use the majority vote strategy [10, 9]; the most voted class is that which is selected.

Hastie and Tibshirani [19] denoted the majority vote strategy as Max-Wins rule and they proposed a new method called Pairwise Coupling (PC). The aim of the method is to find the best approximation of the class posterior probabilities given the posterior probabilities of the pairwise sub-problems. To do so, they transform the problem into an iterative problem where they try to minimize the average weighted Kullback-Leiber divergence between the obtained pairwise estimates and the true pairwise probability values.

Another combination proposal was performed by Platt et al. [30] in order to resolve the unclassifiable regions. They called the new method Decision Directed Acyclic Graph (DDAG); it builds a rooted binary acyclic graph where in each node a classifier discriminates between two classes. The final answer is the class assigned by the leaf node.

$$\begin{pmatrix} +1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & +1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & +1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & +1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{pmatrix} +1 & +1 & +1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & +1 & +1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & +1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

(a) One Vs All (b) One Vs One

Figure 2: OVA and OVO code-matrix

3. Related Works

The first class-binarization strategies were made to solve the problems that some base classifiers have for the multi-class problems, since algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), worked better for binary problems. Therefore, OVA was proposed by Anand et al. [2]. However, due to the good results obtained, the use of these strategies have been extended to other base classifiers, such as Ripper [10] or C4.5 [31].

In several works in the literature, OVO and OVA have been compared, showing that in most of the cases OVO outperformed OVA [10, 20]. Rifkin and Klautau [35] did not consider that these experiments were carefully controlled and they demonstrated that in the case when the OVA classifier is well-tuned it performs as well as OVO.

In some recent works, it is possible to find some reviews related with the class-binarization strategies [27]. Other recent works made empirical studies for different binarization strategies [11, 15]. Both works analyse the behaviour of OVO and OVA for different base classifiers and the results of both works concluded that OVO outperformed OVA. However, neither work dares to contradict Rifkin and Klautau [35] arguing that they did not use fine-tuned classifiers.

One of the criticisms of OVO is that many of the binary classifiers are forced to give wrong answers for many instances, because each classifier must assign every pattern to one of two classes. If a pattern belongs to class i , all the classifiers that are not trained to differentiate this class will cast wrong votes. In order to solve this problem, some authors proposed new approaches which were based on the combination of OVO and OVA. On the one hand, Moreira and Mayoraz [28] proposed to apply OVO taking into account the probability that the new example belonged to each pair of classes. This probability was obtained following the OVA idea: creating a classifier that distinguishes between the two classes and the rest of the classes. On the other hand, García-Pedrajas and Ortiz-Boyer [14] and Ko and Byun [22] proposed independently a very similar idea to combine OVO and OVA. In an interesting motivation García-Pedrajas and Ortiz-Boyer [14] showed that in the majority of the cases the correct class was between the two largest confident outputs of OVA. Thus, in their new method they obtain the two classes with the highest confidence level in OVA first. After that, OVO is applied and a classifier is built only taking into account the cases that belong to these two classes. This method was called All-And-One (A&O) [14].

There are several binarization strategy versions that try to create simpler decomposition strategies. Some of these works try reduce the number of classifiers: basing on a hierarchical structure [32] [26] [16], using dynamic classifiers selection [12][3] or creating the minimal ECOC [4]. And other approaches propose to reduce the number of datapoints [23].

3.1. Different base classifiers

Finally, another drawback of OVO is the weak classifiers. The classical way selects the optimal base classifier for the database and all the sub-problems are classified with this classifier. As there are too many sub-problems, it is possible that this base classifier could have difficulties to distinguish between all of them, thus, the classifiers return wrong results. This raises the question - should the same base classifier be used on all sub-problems? or should sub-problems be tuned independently?

There are few works in the literature that propose to use each sub-problem independently. Szepannek et al. [37] proposed to extend the OVO method selecting the optimal classifier for each pair of classes, where the base classifier which obtains the best result was considered as the optimal classifier. Something similar was proposed by Lebrun [24], where they tried to find the best hyper-parameters of the SVM for each sub-problem. As in SVM there are too many hyper-parameters, they proposed to use an evolutionary algorithm. The experimental results of both works showed that they outperformed the classical individual base-classifier option. Liepert [25] also proposed a similar

approach to Lebrun, where she concluded that the selection of the best models for each binary-classifier does not obtain a significant improvement.

Reid [34] also dealt with this problem in his thesis, where he concluded that in the case of databases in which sub-problem decision boundaries have a similar shape it was better to use the same classifier for all the sub-problems, whereas in the case where the decision boundaries have a different shape it was better to treat sub-problems independently.

4. Preliminary Work

Hanse and Salomon [18] showed that in order to obtain good performance when classifiers are combined, the classifiers should be diverse among them. It is said that two algorithms are diverse when they commit different errors. If two algorithms are not diverse they commit the same errors, whereas if they are diverse they may be able to correct the committed errors.

In this paper we present two new OVO and OVA combinations. A previous step before combining both algorithms is to check whether or not they are compatible. In the literature several diversity measures can be found, but Tang et al. [38] concluded that these diversity measures were ineffective. Therefore, in the next experiment, instead of calculating the diversity between OVO and OVA, we show that OVO and OVA are able to correct the errors that the other algorithm has committed.

4.1. Methodology

In this experiment we calculate the accuracies obtained by OVO and OVA only taking into account the cases where the other algorithm fails. To perform this experiment, we have used the decision trees as base classifiers.

4.2. Datasets

Twenty databases are used to test our hypothesis. All of them are obtained from the *UCI Machine Learning Repository* [8]. The characteristics of the databases are given in Table 1.

Domain	Num. of Instances	Num. of Attributes	Num. of Classes
Abalone	4177	8	29
Annealing	798	38	5
Arrhythmia	452	279	13
Balance	625	4	3
Car	1728	6	4
Cmc	1473	9	3
Dermatology	366	33	6
Ecoli	336	7	8
Glass	214	9	6
Iris	150	4	3
Nursery	12960	8	5
Page-blocks	5473	10	5
Optdigits	5620	64	10
Pendigits	10992	16	10
Satimage	6435	36	7
Segment	2310	19	7
Vehicle	846	18	4
Waveform	5000	21	3
Wine	178	13	3
Yeast	1484	8	10

Table 1: The characteristics of the 20 databases used in this experiment

4.3. Results

In Table 2 we show the results of the compatibility test. In the first two columns we show the accuracy obtained by OVO and OVA, while in the third the accuracy of OVA is shown considering only the cases where OVO makes errors. In the fourth column the accuracy of OVO is shown for the cases that OVA has failed.

	Accuracy of OVO	Accuracy of OVA	Accuracy of OVA when OVO fails	Accuracy of OVO when OVA fails
Abalone	24.946	18.793	12.268	18.910
Annealing	92.383	92.116	25.214	26.508
Arrhythmia	65.885	63.496	29.720	34.319
Balance	78.910	78.910	20.898	20.742
Car	95.914	95.972	34.780	32.725
Cmc	51.460	52.016	24.408	23.597
Dermatology	95.574	91.530	41.702	66.882
Ecoli	81.667	78.571	25.653	35.844
Glass	63.084	60.374	30.566	35.531
Iris	93.467	92.800	1.250	12.500
Nursery	98.622	98.647	6.287	4.172
Optdigits	92.281	87.434	52.325	70.732
Page-blocks	96.824	96.642	17.794	22.202
Pendigits	95.950	94.039	58.541	71.864
Satimage	86.017	83.708	40.617	49.052
Segment	95.039	94.251	45.869	53.228
Vehicle	68.842	68.251	39.939	40.984
Waveform	76.212	74.144	49.187	53.193
Wine	88.202	89.888	54.609	47.018
Yeast	56.267	55.418	17.459	19.071

Table 2: Compatibility between OVO and OVA

It is interesting to note that in the case where one strategy fails the other gets a hit rate higher than 20% in most of cases, which leads us to consider that the methods are compatible and that they could correct some of the errors that the other strategy has made.

5. OVA+OVO

This new method combines the sub-problems obtained applying OVO and OVA decomposition strategies. To take the final decision the results obtained for each sub-problem are combined applying the majority vote, we have called this new method OVA+OVO. On the other hand, we follow the idea of Szepannek et al. [37] where we apply the most reliable base classifier for each sub-problem.

5.1. Decomposition

In our method, we propose to combine the sub-problems obtained with OVO and OVA; on the one hand, we create several sub-problems where the classes are compared by pairs, ignoring the other classes, and on the other hand, we create several sub-problems which compare one class with all the other classes.

In the code matrix of Figure 3 it could be seen the sub-problems obtained in the decomposition phase in a 4-class problem. The 4 columns of the left are the sub-problems obtained with OVA and the next 6 columns are the sub-problems obtained with OVO.

We consider that the combination of these methods could obtain a classifier that outperforms both methods separately for two reasons:

- In Section 4 we have shown that both methods are able to correct the errors committed by the other.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \overbrace{+1 & -1 & -1 & -1}^{\text{OneVsAll}} & \overbrace{+1 & +1 & +1 & 0 & 0 & 0}^{\text{OneVsOne}} \\ -1 & +1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & +1 & +1 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & +1 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & +1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & +1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 3: Code Matrix of OVA+OVO

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{NB} & \text{3NN} & \text{C4.5} & \text{3NN} & \text{C4.5} & \text{SVM} & \text{NB} & \text{SVM} & \text{SVM} & \text{3NN} \\ +1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & +1 & +1 & +1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & +1 & -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & +1 & +1 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & +1 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & +1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & +1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 4: Different base classifier for each sub-problem

- In OVO and OVA methods it is very common for there to be ties between some classes at the time of making the final decision, especially when majority vote is used:
 - In the case of OVA, it is possible that all sub-problems return a negative-class prediction.
 - In the case of OVO, the most voted class could be more than one.

Therefore, we consider that combining their outputs could serve to break some of these ties.

5.2. Best base classifier for each sub-problem

Each sub-problem is treated independently from the others, the optimal base classifier for each one is sought. In a validation process each binary sub-problem is tested with different base classifiers and the base classifier which obtains the best accuracy is selected.

In Figure 4 an example where a different base classifier is applied for each sub-problem can be seen.

5.3. Combination

To take the final decision, we have decided to apply the majority vote; the most voted class is that which is selected. We consider this due to three reasons:

- It is the simplest one.
- As different base classifiers are used for each sub-problem, the combination strategies based on the confidence level are not appropriate because each base classifier confidence level is calculated differently.
- As stated in Galar et al. [11] the majority vote obtains robust results compared with other combination strategies in OVO.

6. Experimental Results

In this section we show the experimental results obtained with different databases. We have compared our method with other state-of-the-art strategies.

6.1. Datasets

We have run our experiments over the same datasets that we have used in the motivation of Section 4. In Table 1 the characteristics of the databases are shown.

6.2. Classifiers

To carry out our experiments we have used some classifiers from a software package for machine learning called Weka (Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis) [17].

Among the classifiers that Weka offers, we have selected the following:

- Naive Bayes [21], statistical learning algorithm. It is based on Bayesian rules and, given that the value of the class is known, it assumes independence between the occurrences of feature values to predict the class.
- J48 (C4.5 clone) [33], decision tree algorithm. It makes a post-pruning phase, based on error based pruning algorithm.
- IBK (K-NN clone) [1], distance based algorithm. An object is classified by a majority vote of its K nearest neighbors. We have used this algorithm when $K = 3$.
- SM0 (SVM clone) [29], kernel methods. It creates a hyperplane where the categories are divided by a clear gap that is as wide as possible.
- JRip (Ripper clone) [5], rule induction classifier. It builds a rule-set by repeatedly adding rules to an empty rule-set until all positive examples are covered.
- MultilayerPerceptron [36], an artificial neural network. It is a feedforward network of neurons which map input vectors to output vectors.

As it can be seen, we have selected classifiers from different approaches in order to give variability to the experimental phase. It is worth saying that in our experiments we have used the default parameters of the classifiers.

6.3. Strategies summarized

In this sub-section we briefly describe the class-binarization strategies that are used for the comparison. It is worth remembering that in all the strategies the best base classifier is selected for each sub-problem.

- One-vs-All (OVA): Each sub-problem compares one class with the rest of classes. The class with the highest confidence level is selected.
- All-And-One (A&O) [14, 22]: Combination of OVA and OVO. First OVA is applied and the two classes with the highest confidence level are selected. A classifier that discriminates between the selected classes is built and the result of the classifier is the final decision.
- Max-Wins [10, 9]: For decomposition OVO is applied: each sub-problem compares two classes between them, ignoring the rest. And the majority vote is used to take the final decision.
- Pairwise Coupling (PC) [19]: PC tries to find the posterior probability of each class ($p_1..p_K$) given the posterior probability of all the pairwise sub-problems (r_{ij}). To do so, the problem is transformed into an iterative problem where the Kullback-Leibler distance between r_{ij} and μ_{ij} is minimized ($\mu_{ij} = p_i/(p_i + p_j)$).
- Decision Directed Acyclic Graph (DDAG) [30]: The DDAG is equivalent to operating on a list. A list is initialized with all the classes. In each step a classifier discriminates between two classes selected from the list, and the class which is not selected is eliminated. The DDAG terminates when only one class remains in the list.

We compared these strategies with our proposed method.

- OVA+OVO: Combination of OVA and OVO outputs. The majority vote is used to take the final decision.

Database	OVA	A&O	Max-Wins	PC	DDAG	OVA+OVO
Abalone	16.553	22.993	26.598	26.426	25.171	26.598
Annealing	98.062	97.929	98.196	98.129	98.085	98.307
Arrhythmia	63.850	65.265	69.292	71.15	68.407	71.018
Balance	90.128	89.840	90.096	90.865	90.641	91.058
Car	96.273	95.914	95.787	95.741	95.845	96.296
Cmc	48.350	49.220	52.831	52.465	51.840	53.646
Dermatology	95.519	97.158	97.541	97.596	97.541	97.432
Ecoli	82.202	83.452	83.095	83.869	83.631	83.810
Glass	64.206	63.458	64.112	65.327	63.458	65.140
Iris	95.333	94.800	94.800	94.800	94.800	94.933
Nursery	99.336	99.384	99.451	99.452	99.431	99.653
Optdigits	98.456	98.480	98.466	98.470	98.395	98.473
Page-blocks	96.707	96.799	96.751	96.667	96.777	96.897
Pendigits	99.250	99.221	99.210	99.207	99.143	99.238
Satimage	89.958	90.126	90.051	90.098	89.961	90.256
Segment	95.844	96.017	96.104	96.329	95.983	96.476
Vehicle	80.567	79.551	78.842	79.433	79.102	79.905
Waveform	84.152	86.436	86.636	86.636	86.636	86.276
Wine	95.955	96.404	96.404	96.404	96.404	96.742
Yeast	56.631	56.536	57.615	57.251	57.049	57.803

Table 3: Accuracy using the six compared methods and different base classifiers for each sub-problem

6.4. Experimental setup

In order to give a real perspective, we have applied 5x2 fold cross validation to each database [6]. But firstly each binarization strategy needs a validation process to select the most accurate base classifiers for each binary sub-problem. Therefore, we have applied 5-fold out for each fold, where we have used 70% as training and 30% as testing.

In Table 3 we show the results obtained for our new method and we have compared them with those obtained with state-of-the-art methods. The best result is highlighted in bold. It can be observed that OVA+OVO obtains the best result in 11 databases.

According to [13], we have used the Iman-Davenport test to detect statistical differences among the different strategies. This test rejects the null hypothesis of equivalence between algorithms since p-value (0.0001) is lower than our α -value (0.1). Thus, we have applied Shaffer post-hoc test in order to find out which algorithms are distinctive among them. Table 4 shows the most relevant results of the test, where “+” symbol implies that the first algorithm is statistically better than the confronting one, whereas “=” means that there are not significant differences between the compared algorithms. It can be seen that OVA+OVO outperforms all the other state-of-the-art strategies with the exception of PC.

7. Motivation through the second approach

In the previous experiment the results obtained by A&O and OVA methods were lower than expected. Rifkin and Klautau [35] showed the strength of OVA when the classifier was well-tuned and we consider that selecting the best base classifier for each sub-problem is a good way to tune the sub-problems. Consequently we have made an analysis in order to find the reason for these low results.

7.1. The strength of OVA

In order to analyze the behaviour of OVA, we have carried out a new experiment. Firstly, we have seen how OVA works by only taking into account the cases where there is only one sub-problem that returns a positive-class

Hypothesis	p-value
OVA+OVO vs OVA	+(1.7640E-005)
OVA+OVO vs A&O	+(0.0005)
OVA+OVO vs DDAG	+(0.0006)
OVA+OVO vs Max-Wins	+(0.0270)
PC vs OVA	+(0.0529)
OVA+OVO vs PC	=(0.3839)
PC vs A&O	=(0.3839)
PC vs DDAG	=(0.3839)
Max-Wins vs OVA	=(0.4409)

Table 4: Shaffer test

prediction. In other words, there is only one case among all the sub-problems in which one class is selected instead of the rest of the classes.

In Table 5 it can be seen in which percentage of the cases OVA takes the final decision under the aforementioned circumstances and which is the accuracy obtained. The results show that a large amount of cases are classified under these circumstances, obtaining high accuracy. Therefore, we deduce that OVA fails with the remaining cases, so they are analyzed.

	Accuracy	Percentage
Abalone	40.1460	0.6560
Annealing	99.0697	97.9955
Arrhythmia	79.2068	71.5929
Balance	95.7456	89.3269
Car	98.0235	94.0046
Cmc	63.3987	51.6768
Dermatology	98.4006	95.5738
Ecoli	87.5366	88.6905
Glass	74.8420	69.6262
Iris	95.8297	99.0667
Nursery	99.8178	98.3071
Optdigits	98.5451	99.7972
Page-blocks	97.8094	97.5516
Pendigits	99.3934	99.5560
Satimage	90.8728	97.7249
Segment	98.2398	94.7619
Vehicle	87.3012	76.8085
Waveform	89.2405	83.2000
Wine	96.9011	96.8539
Yeast	67.2738	59.9730

Table 5: Accuracy and percentage of the cases where OVA takes the final decision when in only one sub-problem the class is selected instead of the rest of the classes

7.2. The weakness of OVA

After the analysis, we have deduced that the reason for the bad results of OVA and A&O is because the type of classifier that is used in each sub-problem has a big influence on the final decision. OVA and A&O obtain each class confident level taking into account only one sub-problem, and in each sub-problem different base classifiers are applied. Each type of classifier uses a different methodology to calculate the confidence level, hence, these confidence

Sub-problem	C_1		C_2	
	θ_i	All	θ_i	All
$\theta_1 - vs - All$	0.33	0.67	0.17	0.83
$\theta_2 - vs - All$	0.20	0.80	0.11	0.89
$\theta_3 - vs - All$	0.07	0.93	0.05	0.95

Table 6: Confidence levels obtained in OVA for each sub-problem for C_1 and C_2 classifiers

levels have different meanings. Some classifiers tend to distribute the confidence level among the classes more equally than others. As a consequence, in the cases where all the output of OVA is negative, the classes obtained using these classifiers are more likely to be selected. We will try to clarify this problem with the following example:

Example: Let us consider a 3-class problem $\{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3\}$ and a new case to be classified. The confidence levels obtained for each OVA sub-problem for classifiers C_1 and C_2 can be seen in Table 6.

It can be observed in Table 6 that in both classifiers, θ_1 obtains the highest confidence levels; as a consequence, θ_1 should be assigned to the new case. Moreover, it is possible to observe that all the classes obtain higher confidence levels with C_1 than with C_2 . So, let us consider that after the validation phase, C_2 is selected for $\theta_1 - vs - all$ and C_1 for $\theta_2 - vs - all$ and $\theta_3 - vs - all$. In this case, θ_2 is the class with the highest confidence level (0.20), so θ_2 is assigned to the new case.

In this example, it can be seen that the classes classified with C_1 have more probabilities to be selected than the classes classified with C_2 . Hence, the final decision could be different, depending on the type of classifier that is selected in each sub-problem. That is why we consider it not fair to compare the confidence levels among them.

In order to avoid this problem, the accuracy obtained for each classifier of the sub-problems in the validation phase, could be used as a confidence level. But we do not consider this appropriate because the accuracy depends on how the classes are distributed. The best differentiated classes are more likely to be selected, because the sub-problems where they take part obtain a higher accuracy in the validation phase.

8. *New One Versus^{All}_{One}* (NOV@)

In the previous section we have shown that it is not a sound alternative to depend on the confidence levels when different base classifiers are used, moreover we have shown the strength of OVA in the case that among the sub-problems in only one of them one class outperforms the rest. Furthermore, in Section 4 it has been shown that OVO is able to correct some errors made by OVA.

Considering these three facts, we propose a new version of OVA where the confidence level is not taken into account; we use the majority vote. As previously mentioned, the problem of the majority vote in OVA is that it is common for there to be ties. In this case, the ties are broken by applying OVO only taking into account the tie-classes. We have denoted this new method as *New One Versus^{All}_{One}* (NOV@). When a new case to be classified arrives there are 3 possibilities:

- If in only one of the sub-problems a positive result is obtained, we consider that it is sufficiently reliable, therefore NOV@ returns this class.
- If in more than one case a positive result is obtained, then there is a tie. Hence, Max-Wins is applied only taking into account the tie classes.
- If all the sub-problems obtain a negative result, we consider that OVA has not enough reliability to take the final decision, so Max-Wins is applied with all the classes.

With this algorithm our aim is to improve OVA's performance. Moreover as we have seen in Table 5 the majority of instances are classified applying OVA, hence our algorithm uses less number of sub-problems than OVO.

9. Experiments with NOV@

We have run this new method with the same characteristics as run in the previous experiments (Section 6). Table 7 shows the obtained results where it can be seen that NOV@ obtains the best result in 12 of the databases, whereas OVA+OVO obtains the best result in 4.

Database	OVA	A&O	Max-Wins	PC	DDAG	OVA+OVO	NOV@
Abalone	16.553	22.993	26.598	26.426	25.171	26.598	26.560
Annealing	98.062	97.929	98.196	98.129	98.085	98.307	98.396
Arrhythmia	63.850	65.265	69.292	71.150	68.407	71.018	72.124
Balance	90.128	89.84	90.096	90.865	90.641	91.058	90.994
Car	96.273	95.914	95.787	95.741	95.845	96.296	96.563
Cmc	48.350	49.220	52.831	52.465	51.840	53.646	53.863
Dermatology	95.519	97.158	97.541	97.596	97.541	97.432	97.377
Ecoli	82.202	83.452	83.095	83.869	83.631	83.810	84.643
Glass	64.206	63.458	64.112	65.327	63.458	65.140	67.009
Iris	95.333	94.800	94.800	94.800	94.800	94.933	95.467
Nursery	99.336	99.384	99.451	99.452	99.431	99.653	99.671
Optdigits	98.456	98.480	98.466	98.470	98.395	98.473	98.452
Page-blocks	96.707	96.799	96.751	96.667	96.777	96.897	97.003
Pendigits	99.250	99.221	99.210	99.207	99.143	99.238	99.221
Satimage	89.958	90.126	90.051	90.098	89.961	90.256	90.030
Segment	95.844	96.017	96.104	96.329	95.983	96.476	96.667
Vehicle	80.567	79.551	78.842	79.433	79.102	79.905	80.922
Waveform	84.152	86.436	86.636	86.636	86.636	86.276	85.948
Wine	95.955	96.404	96.404	96.404	96.404	96.742	96.629
Yeast	56.631	56.536	57.615	57.251	57.049	57.803	58.679

Table 7: Accuracy using the seven compared methods and different base classifiers for each sub-problem

As in the previous experiments, we have applied the Iman-Davenport test obtaining $p\text{-value} < 0.0001$. So we proceed with the Shaffer test. Table 8 shows the most relevant results. The method having the best performance is NOV@, closely followed by OVA+OVO. Both methods improve the remaining strategies significantly with the exception of PC. However, if we compare PC, OVA+OVO and NOV@ applying Wilcoxon signed-rank test by pairwise, we find out that NOV@ significantly outperforms OVA+OVO and PC, and that OVA+OVO outperforms PC. In Table 9 the comparison can be seen.

We have shown in the previous section (Section 7) that we must be careful when we are using strategies that depend on the confidence level when different base classifiers are used. However PC also depends on the confidence levels of the sub-problems and, curiously, PC is the state-of-the-art algorithm that obtains the best results. The difference between A&O and OVA with PC is that A&O and OVA obtain the confidence level of each class only taking into account one sub-problem, while PC takes into account the confidence levels of different sub-problems. This leads us to think that this combination tends to compensate the confidence levels.

10. Conclusion

In this work, we have shown that OVO and OVA strategies are compatible to be combined with each other and based on that we have presented two simple decomposition strategies that combine One-vs-All and One-vs-One strategies using different base classifier for each sub-problem.

The proposed methods has been implemented and tested over 20 databases from the UCI repository, obtaining significant improvements over other state-of-the-art strategies. Moreover, these two methods maintain the simplicity of OVO and OVA methods, which makes these methods the most used class-binarization strategies.

Hypothesis	p-value
NOV@ vs OVA	+(3.4314E-005)
OVA+OVO vs OVA	+(5.0343E-005)
NOV@ vs DDAG	+(7.2924E-004)
NOV@ vs A&O	+(9.9532E-004)
OVA+OVO vs DDAG	+(0.0014)
OVA+OVO vs A&O	+(0.0018)
NOV@ vs Max-Wins	+(0.0455)
OVA+OVO vs Max-Wins	=(0.0532)
PC vs OVA	=(0.1146)
NOV@ vs PC	=(0.2815)
OVA+OVO vs PC	=(0.4068)
PC vs DDAG	=(0.6728)
Max-Wins vs OVA	=(0.6728)
PC vs A&O	=(0.6728)

Table 8: Shaffer test

Hypothesis	p-value
NOV@ vs PC	+(0.0028)
OVA+OVO vs PC	+(0.0172)
NOV@ vs OVA+OVO	+(0.0583)

Table 9: Wilcoxon test to compare NOV@, OVA+OVO and PC by pairwise

Furthermore, comparing our methods with other state-of-the-art algorithms, we have made an empirical study in order to analyze how different class-binarization strategies work when different base classifiers are applied in each sub-problem. We want to emphasize that as each type of classifier calculates the confidence level in a different way one must be careful with the strategies that depend on the confidence levels.

For future work, it would be interesting to analyze how ECOC strategies work when different base classifiers are used in different sub-problems. And after this analysis, it would be interesting to compare them with the two methods proposed.

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